

A study of molecular interaction aniline with benzene + 1-pentanol

P. Sasikumar*, R. Thiagarajan^a and L. Palaniappan^b

Department of Physics, Periyar University College of Arts and Science, Dharmapuri-636 905, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : sasiyanaki123@gmail.com

^aDepartment of Physics, Chikkaiah Naicker College, Erode-638 001, Tamilnadu, India

^bDepartment of Physics (DDE), Annamalai University, Annamalainagar-608 002, Tamilnadu, India

Abstract : The separation efficiency of ternary mixtures aniline + benzene + 1-pentanol has been analyzed using ultrasonic expertises. Ultrasonic velocity, density and viscosity merits have been deliberated at 303 K in the ternary situation of aniline + benzene + 1-pentanol and thermodynamical resemble is applied to enumerate the adiabatic compressibility, free length, free volume, internal pressure and their excess values. The results are illuminated in terms of molecular interaction between the components of the ternary combinations. Observed excess values provide ample evidences for the existence of molecular interactions in the chosen mixture.

Keywords : Molecular interaction, ternary mixtures, velocity, density, viscosity.

Introduction

The ternary liquid mixtures consists of polar and non-polar components are of appreciable importance in understanding the intermolecular interaction between the component molecules and perceive implementation in multiple industrial and technological processes^{1,2}. The discrepancy of ultrasonic velocity and other ultrasonic restrictions along with their excess values of binary (or) ternary liquid mixtures with transmuting the mole fractions of one of the components has been explored by many researchers³⁻⁵.

The study of molecular interaction is said in the organic ternary combinations [aniline (C₆H₅NH₂) + benzene (C₆H₆) + 1-pentanol (C₆H₁₂O)] is distinct interest as it demands alcohol as one of the component. As alcohols are exceptionally polar, they can be assembled to form binary and ternary complexes. Further, they play a predominant character in many chemical reactions due to their potential to undertake self assembling with assorted structure⁶. Benzene and aniline actuality aromatic, and aniline with amino group, act as electron donors. Though the amino group is comparatively a strapping electron-donor, the H atoms in the NH₂ group can also scope the duty of electron-acceptor centers⁷. Hence 1-pentanol with

its hydrophobic and hydrophilic groups can act together with other two components as if the components conduct the electron-donors. In this case, hydrophobic group unveil striking type interactions and the hydrophilic shows repellent type whereas repulsive interaction exist in between the two electron-donors, as net enforcement the ternary system occurrences larger compressibility. In case if aniline behave as an electron-acceptor then it seems that donor-acceptor complexation of the two solutes exist in the alcohol channel wherein all the striking type interactions that leads to a comparatively lower compressibility⁸⁻¹¹. In view of the above outstanding features, a strive has been made to illuminate the molecular interaction study in the ternary liquid combinations of 1-pentanol with benzene in aniline at 303 K.

Experimental

The liquid combinations of various concentrations in mole fraction were prepared by taking AR grade chemicals, which were decontaminate by standard methods¹². In all the systems, the mole fraction of second component, benzene (X₂ = 0.3) was kept fixed while the mole fractions of the persisting two were varied from (0.0 to 0.7) so as to have the mixtures of different composition. There is nothing consequential on fixing the second com-

ponent ($X_2 = 0.3$). The ultrasonic velocity (U) in liquid mixtures have been deliberated using an ultrasonic interferometer (Mittal type, Model F-80) working at 2 MHz frequency with an accuracy of $\pm 0.1 \text{ ms}^{-1}$. The density (ρ) and viscosity (η) are deliberated using a pycnometer and an Ostwald's viscometer respectively with an accuracy of 3 parts in 10^5 for density and 0.001 Nsm^{-2} for viscosity. Using the deliberated data, the acoustical restrictions such as adiabatic compressibility (β), free length (L_f), free volume (V_f), and internal pressure (π_i) and their excess restrictions have been enumerated using the following standard expressions¹³.

$$\beta = (U^2\rho)^{-1} \quad (1)$$

$$L_f = K_T\beta^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

$$V_f = \left[\frac{M_{\text{eff}}U}{\eta k} \right]^2 \quad (3)$$

$$\pi_i = bRT \left[\frac{k\eta}{U} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[\frac{\frac{2}{\rho^3}}{M_{\text{eff}}^6} \right] \quad (4)$$

$$A^E = A_{\text{exp}} - A_{\text{id}} \quad (5)$$

$$A_{\text{id}} = \sum x_i A_i \quad (6)$$

where, K_T is the temperature dependent constant having a value 201.1209×10^{-8} in MKS system, k is a constant equal to 4.28×10^9 in MKS system, unconventional of temperature for all liquids, b is the cubical packing fraction taken as 2 for all the liquids, R is the universal gas constant, T is the innovative temperature, $M_{\text{eff}} = \sum x_i m_i$ where, x is the mole fraction and m is the molecular weight of i -th component and A^E stands for excess property of any given parameter, A_{exp} is the innovative value and A_{id} is the ideal value¹⁴.

Results and discussion

Measured values of density (ρ), viscosity (η) and velocity (U) at 303 K for the ternary system of aniline + benzene + 1-pentanol are given in Table 1. All the measured restitutions increases with increasing mole fraction of aniline. Such non-linear distinction indicates the presence of intermolecular interactions between the components¹⁵.

Among the three components, aniline and 1-pentanol are awaited to involve in strapping interaction due to their

Table 1. The merit of density (ρ), viscosity (η) and velocity (U) of the system : aniline with benzene + 1-pentanol at 303 K

Mole fraction		ρ	η	U
x_1	x_3	(kg m^{-3})	($\times 10^3 \text{ Nsm}^{-2}$)	(ms^{-1})
0.0000	0.7692	933.0	2.2822	1250.0
0.0806	0.6896	939.8	2.2100	1287.0
0.2307	0.5384	951.8	1.8172	1305.2
0.3076	0.4615	958.8	1.7599	1333.0
0.4615	0.3076	970.6	1.6567	1404.0
0.5384	0.2307	976.8	1.7209	1431.1
0.6185	0.1525	983.1	1.8264	1454.7
0.7692	0.0000	995.6	2.2948	1538.3

polar nature¹⁶. Even though benzene is unsaturated, it conducts like a saturated compound generally. Moreover, the presence of benzene molecules as electron donor will gives inflated stability to the carbocation of 1-pentanol and hence they cannot provide any strong interaction. As aniline is having comparatively higher dielectric constant (6.8012) then benzene (2.2620) and both are electron donors, the interaction linking the molecules of aniline with benzene is established to be stronger^{17,18}. The increasing trend of viscosity (η) revealed that the addition of aniline increases the constructive molecular area. The increase in area due to the inclusion of a cyclic molecule (aniline) by substitute linear molecule (1-pentanol) is fully abnormal¹⁹. This may be due to the polar nature of the added component and is reflected in the observed trend of the deliberated restitution.

The perusal of Table 2 disclose that adiabatic compressibility (β), intermolecular free length (L_f) and internal pressure (π_i) are continuously decreases with increasing mole fraction of aniline whereas free volume (V_f) is

Table 2. The merit of adiabatic compressibility (β), free length (L_f), free volume (V_f) and internal pressure (π_i) of the system : aniline + benzene + 1-pentanol at 303 K

Mole fraction		β	L_f	V_f	π_i
x_1	x_2	($\times 10^{10}$ pa^{-1})	($\times 10^{11}$ m)	($\times 10^7$ $\text{m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	($\times 10^{-8}$ Pa)
0.0000	0.7692	6.8595	5.2674	0.4650	2.2602
0.0806	0.6898	6.4240	5.0975	0.8071	2.1510
0.2307	0.5384	6.1654	4.9938	1.5062	1.8423
0.3076	0.4615	5.8745	4.8746	2.6510	1.6858
0.4615	0.3074	5.2266	4.5979	2.6553	1.6358
0.5384	0.2307	4.9993	4.4968	2.5416	1.6258
0.6185	0.1525	4.8067	4.4094	2.2651	1.6225
0.7692	0.0000	4.2445	4.0944	1.3832	1.7152

in decreasing trend²⁰ and a depletion in adiabatic compressibility is a symptom that component molecules are held close to each other. Thus, addition of aniline makes all the components to be very closer. This idea is supported by the decreasing trend of intermolecular free length (L_f).

Free volume (V_f) and internal pressure (π_i) are acting opposite to each other. Free volume (V_f) shows an increasing trend of 0.4 mole fraction, whereas 0.5 mole fraction is a decreasing trend of aniline²¹. Since the π and σ electrons of benzene are readily available for an electrophile, it guides to a suggestion that weak dispersive types as well as dipole-induced dipole type interaction are ascendant between the benzene and other polar molecules.

The addition of aniline with a mixture guides to an opaque structure due to the presence of dipolar type interaction. This subscribes to an increase in free volume values. However, as these can simply form multiplex structures, interior pressure shows a decreasing trend²².

To comprehend the exact type of interaction prevailing between the components, respective excess parameters have been calculated and for the present system, the perusal of Fig. 1 stipulates that excess adiabatic compressibility (β^E) are positive over the absolute mole fraction range. The positive adiabatic compressibility distinctly suggests that weak interactions are prevailing between the components of the mixture. Figs. 2 to 4 the excess

Fig. 1. Mole fraction vs excess adiabatic compressibility at 303 K.

Fig. 2. Mole fraction vs excess free length at 303 K.

Fig. 3. Mole fraction vs excess free volume at 303 K.

Fig. 4. Mole fraction vs excess internal pressure at 303 K.

values are negative over the absolute mole fraction range. The excess free length (L_f^E), free volume (V_f^E) and internal pressure (π_i^E) are also negative whereas both are acting in a similar manner^{23,24}. This distinctly confirms that the maximum number of component molecules get into complexation at this mole fraction.

Conclusion

Weak dispersive and dipole-induced dipole type interactions are originated in the system, and aniline, on adding with the 1-pentanol+benzene is accomplished to associate with other free components as well as with the binary complexes.

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